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DEFINITION OF THE STRESS-DEFORMED STATE OF THIN SHALLOW SHELLS TAKING INTO ACCOUNT PLASTIC DILATANCY

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Annotation: The stress-deformed state of thin shallow shells of positive Gaussian curvature made of dilating materials beyond the elastic limit is studied. Differential equations are obtained that determine the operation of the shell beyond the elastic limit. The results of solving the obtained differential equations are presented. The results of the development of plasticity zones under different loads are presented.

Keywords: dilation, plasticity, differential equation, fluidity, form change, deformations, nonlinearity, stress-deformed state

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ НАПРЯЖЕННО-ДЕФОРМИРОВАННОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ТОНКИХ ПОЛЫХ ОБОЛОЧЕК С УЧЕТОМ ПЛАСТИЧЕСКОЙ ДИЛАТАНСИИ

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Аннотация: Исследовано напряженно-деформированное состояние тонких пологих оболочек положительной гауссовой кривизны из расширяющихся материалов за пределом упругости. Получены дифференциальные уравнения, определяющие работу оболочки за пределом упругости. Приведены результаты решения

полученных дифференциальных уравнений. Представлены результаты развития зон пластичности при различных нагрузках.

Ключевые слова: дилатация, пластичность, дифференциальное уравнение, текучесть, изменение формы, деформации, нелинейность, напряженно-деформированное состояние

At present, among the many structural materials, a rather extensive class of materials stands out, whose mechanical characteristics depend on the type of stress state [1, 2, 4]. These materials include most composite and polymeric materials.

The first theory that formulated the conditions for the limiting state of materials with different resistances was the Coulomb-Mohr theory. Then, already in the 20th century, other criteria for the limit state were proposed, which in essence are modifications of the Mises-Genka hypothesis, using various forms of taking into account the influence of the spherical tensor. The limit state conditions, built based on the previously mentioned theories, contain three material constants, mainly determined from the simplest experiments on tension, compression, and shear. Naturally, such an approach cannot claim to be a universal description of the operation of a wide class of materials. Experimental studies indicate that each hypothesis applies only to a certain narrow class of materials under certain stress states. Much more effective are theories that involve introducing into the strength condition of materials a function of the type of stress state determined by processing experimental diagrams of limit states for various types of the stress state.

To generalize the approach to describing the stress-strain state of differently resisting dilating materials, the plasticity condition can be formulated in a fairly general form [3, 5].

$$F(\sigma_{ij}) = \tau \cdot f(\xi) = k_{\tau}, \quad (1)$$

where $f(\xi)$ - stress state function;

$\xi = \sigma/S_0$ - octahedral normal normalized stress;

$\sigma = \sigma_{ij} \cdot \delta_{ij}/3$ - medium stress;

$S_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \delta_{ij} \cdot \sigma$ - stress deviator;

$\tau = \sqrt{S_{ij} \cdot S_{ij}/3}$ - tangential stress on an octahedral area;

$S_0 = \sqrt{\sigma^2 + \tau^2}$ - modulus of the total stress vector on an octahedral area;

δ_{ij} – Kronecker symbol;

$k_\tau = \sqrt{2/3}\tau_S$, where τ_S – fluidity in pure shear.

The expression for the function that characterizes the type of stress state $f(\xi)$, included in condition (1) is determined individually for each material when processing experimental diagrams of its limit states for various types of the stress state. In particular, for polymethyl methacrylate, this function can be represented by the following mathematical expression [6].

$$f(\xi) = e^{0,424\xi}. \quad (2)$$

The value of the constant k_τ for polymethyl methacrylate included in condition (1) is 58.9 MPa. It should be noted that the qualitative parameter ξ used in expression (1) changes in the interval $[-1;1]$, which allows describing a wide range of stress states.

The solution to the problem of shell bending is carried out based on the theory of small elastic-plastic deformations. When solving the problem, the following prerequisites are accepted: 1) the usual provisions of the technical theory of shell bending are used - the hypothesis of plane normal sections and the hypothesis of a plane stress state; 2) the deformation diagram of the material has a pronounced yield plateau, which makes it possible to apply the model of an ideal elastic-plastic body; 3) loading is considered simple.

The task of studying the stress-deformed state of shells ultimately comes down to solving a system of two nonlinear differential equations [8].

$$\frac{\partial^4 \varphi}{\partial x_1^4} + \frac{\partial^4 \varphi}{\partial x_2^4} + \frac{\partial^4 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} = \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} - K_2 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} - K_1 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 M_{11}}{\partial x_2^2} + \frac{\partial^2 M_{22}}{\partial x_1^2} - \frac{\partial^2 M_{12}}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} = - \left(q + \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_2^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + K_2 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2} + K_1 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_2^2} \right)$$

where q – load intensity;

E – material elasticity model;

K_1 and K_2 – principal curvatures of the shell.

The first expression in the system (3) is the equation of compatibility or continuity of deformations, written in terms of stress functions $\varphi(x_1, x_2)$ and deflections $\omega(x_1, x_2)$, the second is the equilibrium equation written in terms of bending moments M_{ij} , as well as functions of stresses and shell deflections. Moreover, the stress function is directly related to the longitudinal forces N_{ij} by the following dependencies $N_{11} = h \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_2^2}$; $N_{22} = h \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2}$; $N_{12} = -h \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2}$, where h is the shell thickness.

The introduction of the stress state function into the plasticity condition determines the difference between the stresses that cause plasticity in the stretched and compressed sections of the section. In the middle plane, in contrast to the classical scheme of material operation, deformations ε_{ij} occur, due not only to the presence of longitudinal forces in the section but also caused by the displacement of the neutral surface of the shell during bending from its middle plane, due to the difference in stress values that cause plasticity in the upper and lower sections of the section. Therefore, the expression for the deformations of an arbitrary section point that does not belong to the median plane is represented as

$$e_{11} = \varepsilon_{11} - z \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2}; e_{22} = \varepsilon_{22} - z \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2}; e_{12} = \varepsilon_{12} - z \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2}, \quad (4)$$

where ω - deflection of the median plane;

ε_{ij} – deformations in the median plane.

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{du}{dx_1} - k_1 \omega + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\omega}{dx_1} \right)^2, \varepsilon_{22} = \frac{dv}{dx_2} - k_2 \omega + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{d\omega}{dx_2} \right)^2, \\ \varepsilon_{12} = \frac{dv}{dx_1} + \frac{du}{dx_2} + \frac{d\omega}{dx_1} \cdot \frac{d\omega}{dx_2}$$

Expressions for stresses can be written in the following form

$$\sigma_{ij} = k_{ij} (r_{ij} - z \cdot \Delta_{ij}), \quad i, j = 1, 2, \quad (5)$$

where

$$k_{11} = k_{22} = \frac{E}{(1 - \mu^2)}; k_{12} = \frac{E}{1 + \mu}; r_{11} = \varepsilon_{11} + \mu \cdot \varepsilon_{22}; r_{22} = \varepsilon_{22} + \mu \cdot \varepsilon_{11}; r_{12} = \varepsilon_{12}; \\ \Delta_{11} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2}; \Delta_{22} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2}; \Delta_{12} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2}; \\ \chi_{11} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2}; \chi_{22} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2}; \chi_{12} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2}.$$

The position of the neutral plane is determined from the condition that for $z = c_{ij}, \sigma_{ij} = 0$. From here

$$c_{ij} = r_{ij} / \Delta_{ij}. \quad (6)$$

The coordinates of the beginning of the zones a_{ij}, b_{ij} , in which stresses arise that cause plasticity, are determined from the conditions that at $z = a_{ij}, \sigma_{ij} = A_{ij}$, and at $z = b_{ij}, \sigma_{ij} = B_{ij}$.

From here

$$a_{ij} = \frac{k_{ij} \cdot r_{ij} - A_{ij}}{k_{ij} \cdot \Delta_{ij}}, \quad b_{ij} = \frac{k_{ij} \cdot r_{ij} - B_{ij}}{k_{ij} \cdot \Delta_{ij}}. \quad (7)$$

The values of r_{ij} are determined from the condition that the total area of the stress diagram in the section is equal to the corresponding value of the longitudinal force acting in the same section:

$$\text{for one-sided plasticity: } N_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{a_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} dz + \int_{a_{ij}}^{h/2} A_{ij} dz, \quad (8)$$

for double-sided plasticity:

$$N_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{b_{ij}} B_{ij} dz + \int_{b_{ij}}^{a_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} dz + \int_{a_{ij}}^{h/2} A_{ij} dz. \quad (9)$$

The moment values are calculated by integrating the stresses over the shell thickness:

for one-sided plasticity:

$$M_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{a_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} z dz + \int_{a_{ij}}^{h/2} A_{ij} z dz, \quad (10)$$

for double-sided plasticity:

$$M_{ij} = \int_{-h/2}^{b_{ij}} B_{ij} z dz + \int_{b_{ij}}^{a_{ij}} \sigma_{ij} z dz + \int_{a_{ij}}^{h/2} A_{ij} z dz. \quad (11)$$

Considering dependences (5), (10), (11) together and after simple transformations, we obtain expressions for the moments in the form

$$M_{ij} = R_{ij} + S_{ij} \cdot \Delta_{ij}, \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} R_{ij} &= \frac{B_{ij} \left(b_{ij}^2 - \frac{h^2}{4} \right)}{2} - \frac{A_{ij} \left(\frac{h^2}{4} - a_{ij}^2 \right)}{2} + \\ &+ k_{ij} \cdot \frac{r_{ij} (a_{ij}^2 - b_{ij}^2)}{2}, \quad S_{ij} = \\ &= - \frac{k_{ij} (a_{ij}^3 - b_{ij}^3)}{3}. \end{aligned}$$

To describe the stress-strain state of the shell, it is necessary to substitute expression (12) into the second equation of system (3). It should be noted that the components R_{ij} vanish during differentiation and the zones of plasticity propagation along the thickness of the shell a_{ij}, b_{ij} are the same for each specific section, since they are formed by the complex ratio of stresses σ_{ij} , and not by each stress. As a result, it will be convenient to omit the indices for these quantities in further mathematical calculations, adopting the general designations a, b for them. It should be noted that the coefficients k_{11} and k_{22} are equal to each other, and the following dependence connects them with the coefficient k_{12} following the notation adopted in formula (5):

$$k_{11} = k_{22} = k_{12} (1 - \mu) = E / (1 - \mu^2). \quad (13)$$

Taking into account the last remarks and formula (13), we write in expanded form the coefficients S_{ij} , included in equation (12)

$$S_{11} = \frac{E(a^3-b^3)}{3(1-\mu^2)}, S_{22} = \frac{E(a^3-b^3)}{3(1-\mu^2)}, S_{12} = \frac{E(a^3-b^3)}{3(1-\mu^2)}(1-\mu). \quad (14)$$

For the convenience of notation, we select the common factor - S in expressions (14) for the values S_{11}, S_{22}, S_{12} and rewrite these expressions taking into account the last notation

$$S_{11} = S; S_{22} = S; S_{12} = S(1-\mu), \quad (15)$$

where $S = \frac{E(a^3-b^3)}{3(1-\mu^2)}$.

In its physical essence, the value S in expressions (15) is the cylindrical stiffness of the shell section, weakened as a result of the entry of the material into the plastic stage of deformation.

The system of two nonlinear differential equations (3), taking into account the remarks made and the notation adopted in formulas (15), and expression (12), after simple transformations, will be written in the following form

$$S \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^4 \omega}{\partial x_1^4} + \frac{\partial^4 \omega}{\partial x_2^4} + \frac{\partial^4 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} \right) = \left[\left(\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} \right) - \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} - K_2 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} - K_1 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} \right] \quad (16)$$

$$S \cdot \left(\frac{\partial^4 \omega}{\partial x_1^4} + \frac{\partial^4 \omega}{\partial x_2^4} + \frac{\partial^4 \omega}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2} \right) = - \left(q + \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_2^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x_2^2} - 2 \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} + K_2 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_1^2} + K_1 \cdot \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x_2^2} \right)$$

The system of equations (16) determines the operation of a shell made of a dilating material both in the elastic and plastic stages.

Linearization of the system of two nonlinear differential equations (16), when solving shell bending, was carried out by the method of successive loadings, as recommended in [5, 7]. The linearized system of equations (16) will have the following form:

$$\nabla^4 \delta \varphi + \nabla_{K+\chi}^2 \delta \omega = 0, \nabla_{K+\chi}^2 \delta \varphi + S \cdot \nabla^4 \delta \omega - \nabla_q^2 \delta \omega = -\delta q, \quad (17)$$

Where

$$\nabla^4 = \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^4} + \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_2^4} + 2 \frac{\partial^4}{\partial x_1^2 \partial x_2^2}, \nabla_{K-\chi}^2 = (K_2 - \chi_{22}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} (K_1 - \chi_{11}) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} + 2\chi_{12} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2},$$

$$\nabla_q^2 = N_{11} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} + N_{22} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2} + 2N_{12} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2},$$

where $\delta \varphi, \delta \omega$ - increments of the function of the stresses and deflections corresponding to a small increase in the external load δq ; $S, N_{11}, N_{22}, N_{12}, \chi_{11}, \chi_{22}, \chi_{12}$ - the initial characteristics of the system, corresponding to a certain level of external load. The solution of the system

of linearized equations (17) was carried out by the numerical method of finite differences.

The obtained results confirm the fact that the description of plastic bending of shells made of dilating differently resisting materials does not fit into the framework of the classical theory of shell mechanics.

Bibliography

[1] Ainbinder S.B. Effect of hydrostatic pressure on the mechanical properties of polymeric materials / S.B. Ainbinder, M.G. Laka, I.Yu. Majors // Polymer Mechanics. - 1965. No. 1. 65-75 p.

[2] Berezin A.V., Lomakin E.V., Stokov V.I., V.N. Barabanov // Problems of strength. - 1979. No. 2. 60-65 p.

[3] Bozhanov P.V. Investigation of plastic bending of plates made of dilating material / P.V. Bozhanov, A.A. Treshchev // Izv. universities. - Construction. - 2003. No. 3. 18-23 p.

[4] Elsufiev S.A. Studying the deformation of fluoroplastics under conditions of a plane stress state / S.A. Elsufiev, V.M. Chebanov // Research on elasticity and plasticity. - L.: LGU, 1971. Issue. 8. 209-213 p.

[5] Petrov V.V. The method of sequential loading in the nonlinear theory of plates and shells / V.V. Petrov - Saratov: SGU, 1975. 119 p.

[6] Pisarenko G.S. Deformation and strength of materials under complex stress state / G.S. Pisarenko, A.A. Lebedev. - Kyiv, 1976. 416 p.

[7] Potapova L.B. How are limit stresses predicted? / L.B. Potapova, V. P. Yartsev // Mechanics of materials under complex stress state. - M.: Publishing house mechanical engineering - 1, 2005. 244 p.

[8] Timoshenko S.P. Plates and shells / S.P. Timoshenko, S. Voinovsky - Krieger - M.: Fizmatgiz, 1963. 647 p.

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Айнбиндер С.Б. Влияние гидростатического давления на механические свойства полимерных материалов / С.Б. Айнбиндер, М.Г. Лака, И.Ю. Направления // Механика полимеров. - 1965. № 1. 65-75 с.

[2] Березин А.В., Ломакин Е.В., Строков В.И., В.Н. Барабанов // Проблемы прочности. - 1979. № 2. 60-65 с.

[3] Божанов П.В. Исследование пластического изгиба пластин из расширяющегося материала / П.В. Божанов, А.А. Трещев // Изв. университеты. - Строительство. - 2003. № 3. 18-23 с.

[4] Елсуфьев С.А. Изучение деформирования фторопластов в условиях плоского напряженного состояния / С.А. Елсуфьев, В.М. Чебанов // Исследования упругости и пластичности. - Л.: ЛГУ, 1971. Вып. 8. 209-213 с.

[5] Петров В.В. Метод последовательного нагружения в нелинейной теории пластин и оболочек / В.В. Петров - Саратов: СГУ, 1975. 119 с.

[6] Писаренко Г.С. Деформация и прочность материалов при сложном напряженном состоянии / Г.С. Писаренко, А.А. Лебедев. - Киев, 1976. 416 с.

[7] Потапова Л.Б. Как прогнозируются предельные напряжения? / ФУНТ. Потапова, В.П. Ярцев // Механика материалов при сложном напряженном состоянии. - М.: Издательство Машиностроение - 1, 2005. 244 с.

[8] Тимошенко С.П. Пластины и оболочки / Тимошенко С.П., Войновский С. - Кригер - М.: Физматгиз, 1963. 647 с.

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